
**PECULIARITIES AND CHALLENGES OF TEACHING TO
TOURISM STUDENTS IN MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM**

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Abstract: The aim of the article is to define, analyze and suggest ways of solution of the influence of learning foreign languages problems to develop international tourism. It is emphasized that the knowledge of foreign languages is important for the further development of international tourism, because the tourism industry is closely connected with foreign languages. Comparative analyses of different methodologists and scientists' points of views was carried out in literature review to match different approaches of most effective way in teaching foreign language for specialist in tourism industry. For the analysis, pedagogical technologies that are often used in the teaching process and technologies that are little known in pedagogical work, which could be very effective, were selected.

Keywords: FL, productivity, international tourism, tourism industry, foreign language, methodologists, subjects.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, consistent reforms are underway to develop the tourism sector as one of the strategic sectors of the national economy, which in the long term will help to solve such important social and economic tasks as job creation, diversification of the economy and accelerated development of regions, increasing incomes and quality of life of the country's population. Due to the dynamic economic growth of the country, its rich historical heritage, tourist professions

remain one of the most popular today. Modern living conditions contribute to the active development of the tourism industry and service sector. The growing demand for quality tourism and hotel services, as well as services in the service sector determines the need for qualified professionals in these areas. Graduates should have theoretical knowledge, practical skills in their chosen fields of study, readiness to solve professional problems in their respective professional activities, as well as general cultural and professional competences in the areas under study.

When applying for a job in a travel company or a prestigious restaurant, hotel, etc. one of the first questions of the employer will be the question of how many and what foreign languages the applicant speaks for the job. In almost any sphere of life of the society, especially in the work of a tourism manager and hospitality manager, knowledge of a foreign language is of great importance for specialists, because it is a means of communication with representatives of other cultures, including in the field of international tourism and hospitality. Candidates for work in tourism are set high requirements: he must have good experience, be inquisitive, active, and are specified and additional skills, including knowledge of a foreign language. Knowledge of a foreign language helps to compete successfully with other candidates for a vacant position, as employees in the field of tourism should be able to offer their services in a foreign language, primarily in English. This impresses foreign clients and has a positive impact on the reputation of a tourism company and on the productivity of its work. Accordingly, we can assume that the requirements to the candidate for employment are not overstated, but a necessary condition for the productive work of the tourist company [1]. Thus, according to the requirements of profession, graduates in the fields of tourism and service training should have the ability to communicate orally and in writing in foreign languages, be prepared to work in a foreign language environment and carry out intercultural communication in FL as part of their professional activities. Attention should also be paid to the promotion of respect and tolerance for the cultures and customs of other countries and peoples, and tolerance of national, racial and religious differences.

Students in the fields of “Tourism and Service” should be able to master the FL to the extent necessary to obtain information from foreign sources; be able to use their knowledge of FL in their professional activities; be able to master the basics of business communications and speech etiquette. The main goal is the development of professional competence implies the ability of the student to organize his or her foreign-language activities adequately to the situations of professional communication. Obviously, a professionally-oriented approach should be a priority in the training of the students. In modern conditions the teaching and learning foreign languages is focused on an interactive basis, which implies the organization of intensive dialogue between the teacher and preferably students in groups. It happens by means of modeling the situations of real professional communication, creating conditions that are as close as possible to the activities of a specialist in the field of tourism and service.

For the formation of the system of foreign language teaching, there was a need to define the profile of foreign language teaching in university with tourist orientation. The choice of a profile of training is caused by the concept of the educational organization, availability of trained personnel, relevance of this or that profile, social order of the society. According to the scientist-methodologist A.N. Shchukin, the profile of foreign language teaching is a complex type of training in a certain field of knowledge, which depends on the possibility and peculiarities of the educational institution, as well as on the wishes and needs of students studying a foreign language [2]. In modern methods of teaching foreign languages, preschool, school, philological, non-philological, course and distance profiles of foreign language teaching have developed and been justified [2]. To determine the profile of foreign language teaching in a tourism higher education institution, we can compare two of the above, namely, philological and non-philological. According to the concept of the scientist-pedagogue I.L. Bim, the philological profile of teaching allows to provide free knowledge of the language within the borders close to the level of a native speaker and the possibility of professional activity as a teacher, translator, specialist philologist [1]. It can also serve as a basis, foundation for further

specialization, e.g. focusing on more diverse and possibly more demanding specializations.

This type of learning proposes tasks as useful vehicles and instruction in LT. This could be a problem solving activity or a project, but the task should have a clear objective, appropriate content, a working/application procedure, and a set range of outcomes [3]. As learners work to complete a task, they have abundant opportunity to interact. During interaction they facilitate language acquisition, they get to listen to the language which may be beyond their present ability, but which may be assimilated into their knowledge of the target language for use at a later time. Content and language integrated learning presupposes to enhance learners' linguistic competence thanks to a higher amount of a target language exposure. Among most favorably influenced by this kind of learning is learners' lexicon. Through receiving FL input in different content subjects learners acquire more profound knowledge and specialized terminology for their future profession. But we should take into consideration that at vocational colleges we teach 1) general English and 2) specialized English [3]. At the same time content-based instruction is aimed to use of socially oriented themes, represents an effort to link students with the world in which students live.

Conclusion

As we can conclude knowledge of foreign languages is important for further development of international tourism. The tourism industry is closely connected with foreign languages as travelers feel they need to know at least one foreign language. English is an international language not only in tourism, but also in business, education and trade, science and technology. Regardless of the language spoken in a particular country, the role of English remains significant, and along with its importance, culture is transmitted. Summarizing the abovementioned, it should be noted that the non-philological profile of education determines optimal conditions for the functioning of the foreign language teaching system in a tourist

higher education institution, including goals, objectives, content, methods, principles and means of education.

REFERENCE

1. P. Ur, "Course in Language Teaching," and others, Ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996.
2. L. Ploughman, "Formation of intercultural communicative competence of students in the process of professional training," and others, Ed. Russian: Institute of Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2017.
3. U. Yu. Abduvakhobova, Education in Tourism Industry-Challenges and Opportunities, International University of Tourism, Uzbekistan. 2020.
4. Educating the Educators in Tourism. (1996), Tourism education and training series. In: Shepherd, R.A., Westlake, J., Cooper, C.P., Shepherd, R., editors. Paperback. 1st ed. Madrid, Spain: World Tourism Organization. p238.
5. Kvartalnov, V.A. (2000), Pedagogy and Tourism. Moscow: Sovetsky Sport.